

ESSENTIAL OILS FROM LEAVES, TWIGS AND FRUITS OF *AEGLE MARMELOS*

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Two more components, namely, *p*-cymene (17%) and cuminaldehyde (5%), have been found in the essential oil from the leaves of *Aegle marmelos*. The essential oils from the twigs and the fruits of this plant have also been examined. The former contains cineol (40-45%) and α -*d*-phellandrene (34.5%) and the latter contains α -*d*-phellandrene only.

The essential oil from the leaves of *Aegle marmelos* has already been examined by us (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 231) and the following components were reported: α -*d*-phellandrene, cineol, citronellal and citral. When larger quantities were available for work and the fractionation done more efficiently, two more components were identified in it. These are *p*-cymene and cuminaldehyde. Further, with a view to gaining information about the biogenesis of the components, oils were also extracted from twigs and from rind of the fruits of the same plant and the relationship of the components occurring in these parts observed.

The amount of α -*d*-phellandrene in fraction (I) of the oil from leaves was estimated from the weight of the fraction (b.p. 173°-174°). It came to be about 56%. The yield of the nitrosite of this terpene, however, was always much smaller than what should correspond to the above percentage. Judged from the yield of its nitrosite the phellandrene content came to be about 35% of the total oil. Although the yield of the nitrosite is not expected to be theoretical, there is an appreciable difference in the percentage of this terpene arrived at in these two ways. It became therefore clear that this terpene fraction contained besides phellandrene some other hydrocarbon having nearly the same boiling point and identical composition or very nearly the same composition as that of phellandrene. Such a hydrocarbon could be limonene (b.p. 175°), terpineol (b.p. 175°), silvestrene (b.p. 173°-175°) or *p*-cymene (b.p. 175°).

The fraction gave indifferent reactions towards tests for the above named terpenes but gave an indication of the occurrence of *p*-cymene in it; as by Etard's reaction it gave an aldehyde identified as α -*p*-tolylpropionaldehyde (semicarbazone, m.p. 156-57°; cf. Miller and Rhode, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1075; 1891, 24, 1356; Errera *Gazzetta*, 1889, 19, 526). Also oxidation of the fraction yielded an acid which sublimed above 250° and thus appeared to be terephthalic acid. *p*-Cymene was thus identified and clearly its presence could not appreciably affect the carbon and hydrogen content of α -*d*-phellandrene which constituted the chief component of this fraction.

Fraction (III) of the oil from leaves (boiling range above 210°) consisting of citral as the main component polymerised mostly on standing. On steam distillation a portion which escaped polymerisation went into the distillate as an oil. This was identified as cuminaldehyde [b.p. 235°; semicarbazone, m.p. 201°-202° (Walbaum and Ruthig, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1902, ii, 66, 155); phenylhydrazone, m.p. 129°; 3-nitrocuminaldehyde, m.p. 54° (Lippmann and Strecker, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 76; Widman, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 167)].

Essential Oil from the Twigs.—The twigs on distillation gave an oil in 0.06% yield. This oil smelt more camphor-like than the oil from the leaves and distilled almost completely between 175° and 176° and contained cineol (m.p. of the addition product with resorcinol, 85°-87°; cf. Baeyer and Virck, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1269). The other component was identified as α -d-phellandrene (nitrosite, m.p. 113°). The proportion of these two components in the oil are approximately 45% and 35% respectively.

Essential Oil from the Fruits.—Essential oil was also obtained by steam distillation of the rind of the ripe fruits of this plant. 200 Lbs. of the fruit gave 24 lbs. of the rind from which 6 c.c. of the essential oil were extracted. With such a small amount fractionation was not attempted. A nitrosite was prepared from this oil which after recrystallisation melted at 113°, from which the presence of α -d-phellandrene in this oil was inferred. There was no positive indication for the occurrence of cineol and citral or any other aldehyde in this oil.

The following table gives the components so far identified in the essential oils from leaves, twigs and rind of the fruits of the plant *Aegle marmelos*.

No.	From leaves.	From twigs.	From fruits.
1.	α -d-Phellandrene, 35% (nitrosite, m.p. 113°).	1. α -d-Phellandrene, 34.5%	α -d-Phellandrene only
2.	Cineol, 3% (addition compounds with resorcinol, m.p. 85°-87°; iodol, m.p. 112° and phosphoric acid).	2. Cineol, 40-45%	—
3.	p-Cymene, 17%	—	—
4.	Citronellal, 21% (semicarbazone, m.p. 84°)	—	—
5.	Citral, 10% (semicarbazone, m.p. 163°)	—	—
6.	Cumin aldehyde, 5% (semicarbazone, m.p. 201-202°; phenylhydrazone, m.p. 129°; 3-nitrocuminal, m.p. 54°)	—	—

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Essential Oil from the Leaves

Identification of p-Cymene in Fraction (I): Etard's Reaction.—To 5 c.c. of the fraction, dissolved in 25 c.c. of carbon disulphide and cooled in a freezing mixture, was added dropwise an ice-cold solution of chromyl chloride (9 g.) in 25 c.c. of the solvent, care being taken not to allow the temperature to rise above 0°. A dark coloured sandy solid separated which was filtered, washed with carbon disulphide and then dried. It was then treated with ice-cold water and shaken with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate, as a result of which an oily liquid separated. It was extracted with ether and after drying the ethereal solution over anhydrous sodium sulphate the solvent was removed. The residual liquid (about 1 c.c.) boiled at 221°-222°.

It reduced Fehling's solution and formed a semicarbazone which on recrystallisation from chloroform melted at 156-57°. From the boiling point of the aldehyde and the melting point of the semicarbazone it was identified as α -p-tolylpropaldehyde.

Oxidation.—The fraction (5 c.c.) was refluxed with a mixture of potassium dichromate (5 g.) and sulphuric acid (50%, 25 c.c.) for 24 hours. After cooling, the product was poured in water, when a solid amorphous acid separated which did not melt even

up to 250° , but sublimed without melting. It also gave a precipitate with barium chloride, insoluble in acids. The compound was inferred to be terephthalic acid.

Identification of Cumin Aldehyde in Fraction (III).—On distilling fraction (III) at atmospheric pressure some citral distilled over but most of it polymerised. In an attempt to recover citral from the polymerised residue by steam distillation, a liquid aldehyde distilled with steam which had an entirely different aroma from that of citral. It was extracted with ether and on removal of the solvent it distilled without decomposition or polymerisation at 235° . It formed a semicarbazone which on recrystallisation from chloroform melted at 201° - 202° . It also formed a phenylhydrazone which crystallised from absolute alcohol and melted at 129° .

3-Nitrocumin Aldehyde.—The mixture (1 c.c.) of fuming nitric acid (2 parts) and sulphuric acid (conc., 1 part) was thoroughly cooled and added to 0.5 c.c. of the ice-cold aldehyde and the mixture kept in ice and salt. A yellowish gummy solid separated which was filtered, dried and then recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 54° .

Essential Oil from the Twigs

The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of green twigs from a copper still provided with a copper condenser. The distillate was extracted with carbon tetrachloride and after drying the extract over anhydrous sodium sulphate the solvent was distilled off. Fifteen kg. of twigs yielded 10 c.c. of the oil. On fractionation almost the whole of the oil passed between 173° and 175° .

Identification of Cineol: Cineol-phosphoric acid Addition Compound.—To 1 c.c. of the oil cooled in a freezing mixture was added syrupy phosphoric acid (d 1.65, 2 c.c.), similarly cooled and the mixture shaken well. A solid compound separated which became harder on further cooling.

Cineol-resorcinol Addition Compound.—Resorcinol (0.5 g.) was added to 1 c.c. of the oil and the mixture slightly warmed to dissolve the former. On cooling fine tubular crystals separated which after recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 85° - 87° .

Estimation of Cineol.—The oil (8 c.c.) was shaken thoroughly with a 50% solution of resorcinol and the mixture kept overnight, when a solid addition compound separated. The aqueous layer and the solid addition compound were separated and each treated with a 10% solution of caustic soda, when an oily liquid separated. It was extracted with ether and the solvent distilled off after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residual liquid (about 3.5 c.c.) distilled at 176° (b.p. of cineol).

Identification of α -d-Phellandrene.—The oil remaining after the removal of cineol in the form of its addition compound with resorcinol, was washed with water till free from resorcinol and then dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and distilled, b. p. 173° - 174° ; 8 c.c. of the oil yielded about 3 c.c. of the liquid free from cineol. It did not reduce Fehling's solution, but formed a nitrosite.

Nitrosite of α -d-Phellandrene.—To 2 c.c. of the fraction, dissolved in 4 c.c. of petroleum ether, was added a solution of sodium nitrite (2 g. in 3 c.c. of water) and the mixture after cooling in ice was acidified with 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid. At once a flocculent precipitate separated which was filtered, dried, dissolved in the least amount of chloroform and precipitated by the addition of methyl alcohol. On recrystallisation from ethyl acetate it melted at 113° .

Essential Oil from the Rind of the Fruits

The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of the rind of the fruit in the manner described above in the case of twigs. The oil (6 c.c) was obtained from 24 lbs. of the rind. On distillation the whole oil passed at 174° - 175° .

It showed indifference towards the tests for cineol and the aldehydes. However, it formed a nitrosite which melted after recrystallisation at 113° . From the boiling point of the fraction and the melting point of its nitrosite, it was identified as α -d-phellandrene.

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